

Influence of Slub Yarn Characteristics on Yarn Properties

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Abstract:

In the dynamic landscape of the textile industry, particular varieties of fancy yarns are witnessing a surge in demand, with slub yarn emerging as a prominent player. Slub yarn offers an appealing aesthetic demand that resonates with fashionable market preferences. Generally, slub yarn production involves altering the speed of back and middle rollers while overfeeding fibers into the main drafting zone, maintaining the speed of the front roller constant. The resulting yarn properties are intricately linked to the overfeeding rate, influencing its appearance and performance characteristics.

In this paper slub yarn parameters like slub per metre and slub count are taken as variables to study its effect on strength, elongation, unevenness, imperfection value and hairiness index of yarn. The measurements of the yarns were made on the fancy yarn profile Uster Tester 5 and the Uster Tensojet devices. The values of the test result were analyzed and evaluated statistically. The experiment showed that the above variables of slub shows significant effect for all the properties except breaking elongation%.

Keywords: *Imperfection Value, Slub count, Slub per metre, Slub population, Unevenness*

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1. Introduction

Slub yarn, a distinctive variant in the realm of textile engineering, has garnered significant attention for its irregular texture and unique aesthetic appeal. Characterized by intermittent thickened sections along its length, slub yarn deviates from conventional yarn structures, offering designers and manufacturers a versatile tool for creative expression in fabric design. As the textile industry continues to evolve, slub yarn has emerged as a sought-after choice, aligning with shifting consumer preferences towards novel and visually intriguing textiles.

The production of slub yarn involves deliberate manipulation of the spinning process, typically achieved by varying the speed of back and middle rollers while overfeeding fibers into the main drafting zone, while maintaining the speed of the front roller constant. This controlled irregularity results in the formation of slub intervals within the yarn, imparting it with a distinctive tactile and visual texture. Various production techniques, including traditional methods and modern advancements such as air-jet spinning and core-spun yarns, contribute to the diversity of slub yarn types available in the market.

The significance of slub yarn in the textile industry is underscored by its ability to enhance fabric texture, appearance, and overall tactile experience. Its irregular structure introduces depth and dimensionality to fabrics, transforming ordinary textiles into captivating pieces of art. Furthermore, slub yarn's versatility extends beyond aesthetics, influencing performance properties such as abrasion resistance, pilling propensity, and dye absorption, thereby impacting the functionality and durability of the end product.

2. Material and Methods

2.1 Materials

For this experiment roving of 1.0 hank, 65/35 polyester-cotton blend with staple length of 29mm-cotton and 38mm-polyester is procured for the trial.

2.2 Methodology

Using modern fancy attachment device attached to drafting system of ring frame, nine samples as per the market trends were produced for the study by developing electronic programme (EP) compatible with ring frame machine parameters.

Table 1: Process Parameters on Ring Frame

Speed (RPM)	9000	
Twist per inch	20.98	
Traveller weight	2/0 LRT	

Table 2: Design of Experiment to produce slub yarn

Slub Count (Ne)	12	14	16
Slub/mtr	4	6	8

Taugachi Design was used to study the main effect of above factors on yarn properties. With 2 factors (slub count and slub/mtr) having 3 levels each, 3² Factorial experiment with L9 orthogonal design was planned. Accordingly nine slub yarns as shown in table 3 for the study were manufactured keeping slub length of 4 cm constant.

2.3 Testing

Strength & elongation were measured on Uster tensojet testing instrument. Total 100 measurements of each combination of samples (10 tests from 10 cops) were taken for the study to see the effect. Fancy yarn structural properties were measured on Uster 5 with fancy profile module. The results obtained were analyzed using the technique General Linear Model (GLM) and graphs were obtained by Minitab software.

3. Result & Discussion

After manufacturing the yarn samples as per the Taguchi design, samples were, evaluated for different properties as tabulated in table 3.

Table 3: Yarn properties of slub yarn

Slub/mtr	Slub count (Ne)	Slub distance (cm)	Count base (Ne)	Avg count (Ne)	Rkm	Elongation %	U%	Imperfection value (IPI)	Hairiness index (HI)
4	12	20.69	37.84	27.43	20.02	9.92	34.29	23014	6.72
4	14	20.46	35.78	27.61	21.37	10.16	32.36	18196	6.74
4	16	20.36	34.66	27.76	21.65	10.50	29.62	16948	7.08
6	12	12.22	39.42	27.27	18.56	10.12	37.27	23329	6.45
6	14	13.34	36.52	27.48	19.61	10.14	33.81	20886	6.49
6	16	13.77	35.72	27.56	21.18	10.18	31.52	18435	6.56
8	12	7.86	42.43	27.09	16.96	9.42	42.00	27717	6.24
8	14	8.89	39.08	27.28	17.32	9.47	36.62	24055	6.35
8	16	8.24	37.32	27.37	19.11	9.52	32.82	20466	6.46

3.1 Effect on average count of slub yarn

Figure 1: Average count of slub yarn

From the above graph, it is clear that as the slub/mtr increases the average count of yarn goes on coarser side due to increase in the fibre content in the yarn. It is also clear that as slub count increases, yarn becomes finer and fibre mass in yarn decreases therefore average yarn count goes to finer one. Statistically analysis shows that both the factors have significant effect on average count of yarn.

3.2 Effect ofon tenacity (Rkm) of slub yarn

Figure 2: Tenacity of slub yarn

Slub/mtr and slub count has significant effect on breaking strength of yarn. As the slub per metre increases, proportion of thin place before and after slub increases causing decreases in the strength of yarn. As the slub count becomes finer increasing trend in the strength of yarn due to proper binding of fibers at slub region gives more compact yarn sustaining more load. More the fibre friction more increases in the yarn strength. It is seen from less number of slubs and finer slub in the yarn.

3.3 Effect on elongation of slub yarn

Statistically there is no significant effect of slub count and slub per metre on breaking elongation percentage of slub yarn. From figure 3, it is seen that as the slub/mtr increases elongation percentage of yarn reduces as the base yarn contribution will be less and also base yarn count goes on finer side introducing weak places. Increases in slub count increases the elongation % of the yarn as number of fibres in the cross section will be less and contributes better twist which gives more breaking elongation.

Figure 3: Breaking Elongation of slub yarn (%)

3.4 Effect on Unevenness of slub yarn

Figure 4: Unevenness of Slub Yarn

Statistically slub per mtr and slub count has significant effect on U% of the yarn. From figure 4, it is clearly seen that as the slub/mtr increases U% of the yarn increases. During base yarn and slub part formation change in draft force is there, which causes unevenness is more. As the slub population increases the number of change in draft from base to slub will increases giving raise to uneven yarn.

Increases in slub count from coarse to finer gives reduction in U % of the yarn. Finer slub having more twist propagation than the coarser slub, gives yarn compactness and fibre strand consolidation effect. This effective cohesion offiner slub gives better U% as compare to coarser slub.

3.5 Effect on Imperfection of slub yarn

Figure 5: Imperfection value of slub yarn

From figure 5, it is clear that as the slub per metre increases the IPI value increases. As the slub per metre increases the base yarn count goes on finer side, so during base yarn count formation as there is more reduction in mass per unit length & also the twist propagation is also more. As slub frequency increases the variation in draft also increases i.e frequency of acceleration & deacceleration will be more so this frequent variation in drafting determines thin places in yarn.

As the slub count goes finer side the IPI value is going to decreases. With finer slub count, less number of fibres in cross section gives better fibre cohesion and twist insertion with less imperfection value. Slub per metre & slub count have significant effect on IPI value of yarn.

3.6 Effect on hairiness index of slub yarn

Here from figure 6, it is clear that as the slub per meter increases the hairiness index of the yarn increases. For hairiness particularly twist plays an important role and as the frequency of slub per meter increases the acceleration and deceleration of rollers for overfeeding of fibers at slub part will be more and the amount of twist with inserted will be vary as the size of the yarn i.e. no. of fibers in yarn cross section vary for slub part & base part. As slub part is less twisted part as compare to base part, so with higher no. of slubs fiber in slub part will be more which is less twisted & the base part is highly twisted. So with less twist the fibre arrangement will not be proper & more

twist concentrated in base part there will be possibility of fibre breakage which contribute to the yarn hairiness. From figure 6, it is clear that with finer slub count hairiness index reduces. For hairiness twist plays an important role as with finer slub count there is better twist propagation which gives less hairiness.

Figure 6: Hairiness Index of slub yarn

4. Conclusion

We can conclude that the fancy slub yarns particularly with less slub population & finer slub count contributes with better yarn properties in terms of strength, elongation, unevenness, imperfection value & hairiness index. Equally it is well known for its appearance, so the slub yarn with coarser slub count & maximum slub population gives better view & appearance in the fabric.

References:

[1] B. Manjunath, P. Kadole, S.Aparaj., “Impression of fancy yarns developed at spinning stage”, *Asian Textile Journal*, **20**(6), 46, (2011)

[2] B .Manjunath, S.Kulkarni, M.Guidyawar., “ Studies on physical properties of slub yarns”, *Spinning Textiles*, (9),118, (2017)

[3] S. Perulyte., “Fancy yarns: efforts to methodize, problems and new suggestions”, *Material Science*, **10**(1), 85, (2004)

[4] F.Testore, M.Guala., “Effect yarns: Properties and parameters”, *Journal of Textile Institute*, **80**(3), 377, (1989)

[5] S.Iqbal, P. Pramanik., “Fancy yarns: Slub & Multicount”, *The Indian Textile Journal*, (9), 24, (2009)

[6] R.Singh, V.K.Kothari., “Progress in nonconventional yarn manufacturing system”, *The Indian Textile Journal*, (8), 72, (2010)